

TIME-LAPSE X-RAY MICROTOMOGRAPHIC IMAGING OF COMPRESSIVE FAILURE IN CARBON FIBRE-EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The relatively low compressive strength of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRPs) caused by kink bands has limited its use in primary load-bearing structures. In this paper, the evolution of kink bands has been captured in notched unidirectional (UD) T800 carbon fibre/epoxy composite under four-point bending (FPB) test. The sequence of damage mechanisms occurred in the three-dimensional (3-D) volume has been observed with time-lapse X-ray micro-tomography (μ CT). The evolution of kink bands is significantly slowed down in the compressive region of the sample under FPB loading. The fibre buckling failure has been observed to propagate until the onset of fibre micro-buckling. The primary kink band, once formed, has been found to maintain its width and orientation under further loading. Multiple kink bands have been observed to originate from a primary narrow kink band. The sequential development of primary kink bands and conjugate kink bands has been found to realign the fibres in between along the original fibre direction. These experimental findings of the kink-band formation process could be used for the development of more reliable analytical and numerical models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been increasingly applied in the aircraft and aerospace industries to replace conventional metal materials [1]. On one hand, the specific strength and stiffness of composite materials is higher than alloys, which can significantly reduce the weight of aircrafts. On the other hand, the shape and mechanical properties of composite materials can be easily tailored according to specific requirements for different parts on the aircraft. CFRP materials composed of high-strength carbon fibres and high-temperature thermoset resins have gained popularity in recent years because of their outstanding mechanical properties and insusceptibility to extreme environmental conditions.

Although the tensile strength of CFRP materials has increased steadily in recent years, the compressive strength of these materials is often 40% lower than their tensile strength, which is still a problem in structural design [2]. A number of studies have focused on the investigation into the damage mechanisms in the compressive failure, and the interaction between these damage modes. The occurrence of kink bands caused by fibre micro-buckling has been found to be the key mechanism resulting in premature and catastrophic failure under compressive loading [3].

As early studies were limited to post-mortem observation by serial sectioning combined with optical microscopy or scanning electron microscopy (SEM), the evolution of kink bands was proposed

based on the post-failure damage patterns [4]. With the help of in-situ loading jigs, the development of kink bands has been observed on the sample surface while it is loaded under compression. Vogler and Kyriakides [5] and Pimenta *et al.* [6] observed kink-band propagation along the kink-band boundary direction and the morphology of multiple kink bands on the ground surface of UD CFRP samples. Hapke *et al.* [7] evidenced the sudden nature of kink-band formation. They observed in two sequential SEM images of the sample surface that kink band had formed and propagated over $100\mu\text{m}$ in 0.2s. In these studies, the observation of the evolution of kink bands is constrained in two dimensions from the sample surface. There is still a need for the understanding of the morphology and development of kink bands in three dimensions.

X-ray μCT is an advanced non-destructive testing technique to characterise the 3-D microstructures of materials and components. It has proved to be effective to assess internal defects and damage in CFRP materials [8]. The 3-D morphology of kink bands has been visualised in our previous study on the T700 carbon fibre/epoxy composite failed under axial compression [9]. Multiple kink bands have been observed to be concentrated at one side of the rod sample. However, due to the limited information that can be obtained from the post-failure study, it is difficult to determine the evolution of multiple kink bands.

In this study, the aim is to investigate the formation of kink bands using time-lapse X-ray μCT with *in situ* loading. The development of kink bands is observed at the compressive zone under FBP load. The understanding of kink-band formation in 3-D provides insightful contribution to the establishment of strategies to improve the compressive strength of CFRP composites by depressing kink-band formation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Composite manufacturing

The carbon fibre/epoxy laminate used in this project was manufactured from UD T800H/MTM28-1 pre-pregs supplied by Umeco Structural Materials Ltd. 32 plies of $300\text{mm}\times 300\text{mm}$ were laminated into a 4mm thick UD panel. The fibre volume fraction of the laminate was measured by the acid digestion method, which was 0.55.

Figure 1: Schematic of the sample geometry and four-point bending loading. (unit: mm)

2.2 Sample preparation

Samples with nominal dimensions of 25mm in length, 2mm in width and 4mm in thickness were cut from the laminate using a diamond saw. Figure 1 shows the schematic of the sample geometry. Fibres lie in the X direction. Each sample was notched at the centre of its length with disc cutting wheels (two cutting wheels were used together to make a wider notch) on a precision cutting machine. The notch was about 0.8mm wide and 2mm deep.

2.3 In situ four-point bending test

FPB test was performed in the Deben CT5000 rig, and the loading was controlled by the Microtest software. As shown in Figure 1, the supporting span is 20mm and the loading span is 7.5mm. The rollers are 5mm in diameter. The sample was loaded at 0.1mm/min by displacement control. The loading was interrupted when damage was observed in the radiograph. The μ CT scan was started after the load became relatively stable, which was normally 10 minutes after each load stop. During each scan, the displacement was maintained, but the load was relaxed to some extent because of the inherent material property.

2.4 X-ray microtomographic imaging and data analysis

The X-ray μ CT scans were conducted on the Zeiss Xradia Versa machine with *in situ* loading in the Henry Moseley Imaging Facility. Figure 2 shows the scan set-up with the rig. For the sample discussed in this paper, five scans were taken at different loading steps. The tube of the rig and the rollers transferring the load were made of glassy carbon. With the rig tube in the way between the source/detector and the sample, the energy level and exposure time needs to be higher than ex-situ experiments, in order to obtain imaging data with good enough quality to examine the features at the fibre scale. The sample was scanned at 80kV with the power of 7W, and the voxel size was 1.8 μ m. 1001 projections were taken in the 360 $^\circ$ rotation, and the exposure time for each projection was 22s, which resulted in a total scan time of about 8 hours. Reconstruction was performed in the TXM Reconstructor software. The reconstructed data was then imported to the Avizo 8.0 software for 3-D data analysis.

Figure 2: μ CT scan set-up in the Zeiss Xradia Versa machine with the Deben CT5000 loading rig.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Time-lapse observation of the damage process

For the sample discussed here, five scans were taken at cross-head displacement of 0mm, 0.31mm, 0.38mm, 0.44mm and 0.51mm, corresponding to the steps 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 on the load-displacement curve respectively, as shown in Figure 3. The peak between step 3 and 4 is due to signal error. As the sample was loaded under FPB, the upper part of the sample was under compressive load along the fibre direction, which was induced by the bending moment. Thus, in this region the condition is similar to the axial compressive loading in UD composite.

Figure 3: Cross-head load-displacement curve of the FPB test.

Figure 4 shows the X-ray μ CT XZ slice images in the centre of the sample in steps 1, 2, 3 and 4. The sequence of damage modes observed is as follows:

- In step 1, fibre failure due to buckling is observed close to the left corner of the notch.
- In step 2, the fibre failure propagates from the unsupported notch surface layer to the sub-layers, and slight fibre micro-buckling is visible close to the right corner of the notch.
- In step 3, the fibre failure on the left side locks-up, while a primary kink band forms lower than the significant fibre micro-buckling at the right notch corner accompanied by a split.
- In step 4, multiple kink bands form from the primary kink band and the split has broadened considerably in the Z direction to form a parallelogram shape. The elongation in the X direction is marginal.

3.2 Kink bands

Kink bands defined by broken fibre segments have been formed in the sample due to the compressive stress in the fibre direction. The kink bands discussed here are all lying in the XZ plane, which are considered as out-of-plane kink bands. The formation of out-of-plane kink bands is due to the less lateral constraining and support to the fibres [10] near the notch surface, which facilitates fibres to buckle outwards into the notch.

Kink-band geometry

The geometrical parameters of the kink bands have been measured in different XZ slice images through the sample, including the kink-band width (ω), the fibre rotation angle within the kink band (ϕ) with reference to the X direction and the kink-band boundary angle (β) with reference to the Z direction. It is found that ω is in the range of 15-125 μ m, which equals 3-25 fibre diameters (the fibre

diameter of the T800 carbon fibre is 5 μm). In addition, it is observed that ϕ is from 25° to 70° and β is from 0° to 35° for the kink bands in the final stage. The comparison of these parameters for the primary kink band in different stages reveals that the kink band geometry barely changes once it forms, which has also been observed by Vogler and Kyriakides in AS4 carbon fibre/PEEK system [11]. Furthermore, two types of kink bands have been found in this sample – kink bands with parallel and non-parallel boundaries. For the non-parallel kink bands, one of the boundaries is almost perpendicular to the fibre direction, which is found to be formed by the fibre breakage at the maximum deflection point.

Figure 4: X-ray μCT XZ slice images of the same position in different steps. (a) Step1, (b) step2, (c) step3 and (d) step 4. Fibre buckling failure, splitting and kink bands are observed at different stages.

Multiple kink bands

The morphology of multiple kink bands observed here is similar to the observation in T700 carbon fibre/epoxy composite failed under axial compression [9]. In the present study, the evolution of multiple kink bands has been captured. It has been found that the narrow kink band on the right is the primary band while the other narrow kinks and the wide kink zone are secondary ones. Three individual narrow bands, each of which is around 20 μm wide, have formed within the wide band. It has been found that under further loading, the boundaries of the primary kink band have not propagated much along the boundary orientation in the XZ plane.

Conjugate kink bands

Conjugate kink bands have been observed in many studies, however the sequential development of primary and conjugate kink bands inside the composite has never been observed. Conjugate kink

bands have formed below the lock-up position of the initial fibre buckling damage zone. The formation of multiple kink bands has also been observed in the conjugate kink bands below the left tip of the split. As the sample has been restrained by the four loading rollers in the Z direction, the large displacement in Z direction induced by the primary kink needs to be accommodated, resulting in the formation of the conjugate kink bands [4]. This can be evidenced by the finding that along with the formation of the conjugate kink bands, the fibres in between the primary and conjugate kink zones have been realigned along the X direction with the uplifting of the wedge volume.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the time-lapse X-ray μ CT analysis of the evolution of kink bands in UD T800 carbon fibre/ epoxy composite has been achieved via *in situ* FPB loading. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The evolution of kink bands is significantly slowed down in the compressive region of the sample under FPB loading. The propagation of kink bands inside the sample can be observed via μ CT.
- The fibre buckling failure close to the left notch corner has been observed to propagate until the onset of fibre micro-buckling close to the right notch corner.
- The primary kink band, once formed, has been found to maintain its width and orientation under further loading. In addition, the band-boundary cracks have barely propagated in the plane where the kink bands lie.
- Multiple kink bands originate from a primary narrow kink band.
- Conjugate kink bands have been found to form after the primary kink bands.

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